

Research Article

Smartphone Usage in Lecture Hall: Impact on University Learning

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Abstract

Most PG or technical graduation students use laptops, tablet PCs, and smartphones. Today, every student has a smartphone; it has become a social status for them. In this connection, we have conducted a study on the usage of smartphones among the students of Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati. Smartphones have become integral to everyone's life, especially in educated people's lives. A smartphone is an advanced tool; it brings the whole world into our palm. It gives knowledge and entertainment. Most students use their smartphones for entertainment and social connection through social media rather than receiving and making calls. Only a few students use smartphones to watch educational videos on YouTube. They know its merits and demerits and its effect on life. However, they do not hesitate to use it in the classroom. The study's findings on gender differences in using smartphones for knowledge or entertainment and essential will be discussed in detail.

Keywords: Smartphones, AI features, Internet, University, Students, Classroom.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Today, smartphones are prevalent and have become ornamental assets for university students. Before joining the university campus, most students ask their parents for a smartphone and finally enter with it. Before starting the academic program, students will form a social group through social media and connect with the help of smartphones. Nowadays, university students feel that they can survive anywhere with smartphones in their hands. Intelligent gadgets like laptops, tablet PCs, and multipurpose smartphones are essential. Everyone should accept the benefits of those gadgets, especially smartphones. Students, youth, working/non-working women, and senior citizens, whomever it may, if they have a smartphone, will easily connect through it. They use it for security and to collect information quickly, like educational, general, inspirational, or spiritual, from anywhere in the world. The smartphone has other shades, which can also negatively affect the student's future. It depends on the student's mentality and content use. When students use smartphones during academic activities such as lectures, seminars, or in the classroom, it often leads to disruptions, diversion, and loss of concentration. This can significantly hinder academic performance and create challenges for the teachers or trainers. The critical nature of these academic sessions makes it imperative for students to maintain focus, and smartphone use can significantly hinder this. Too much use of smartphones and depending on them may affect human lives from many angles; mentally and physically, they have to suffer a lot. Smartphone use while driving may lead to road accidents.

Smartphones are becoming an addiction in youth; overdependency on them also causes emotional stress, spoils the relationship, and lowers the student's studying ability.

Though smartphones can be the best source of educational knowledge, students often think about missed calls, WhatsApp messages, Facebook notifications, and Instagram notifications, even in the classroom and at lunch. They try to check those notifications on social media platforms and give replies and comments. Some backbench students are playing games, ignoring lectures in the classroom, and losing consent in their studies.

Need of the electronic gadgets:

From the outset, academicians worldwide have been exploring the role of technology in information gathering. Oberman, Dean of Library and Information Services at the Plattsburgh State University of New York, emphasised in his book LIBRARY TRENDWWINTER (1991) that students should be equipped with critical thinking skills to solve the overloaded problem of information and take advantage of the electronic environment.

Libraries in universities provide information in book formats for the students and faculty. Librarians can help students conduct library research and evaluate what they find in a systematic manner. However, searching is a time-consuming process, and the students have to search day together to find related information. In recent years, many reports from different surveys, have identified the importance of technology. Universities and faculty members all over the world reveal that technology should be adopted day to day. Every technological and electronic gadget regarding education should be provided in the university. When technology is added to the student's skill and ability, then research and study will speed up.

In recent days, tonnes of information have been available on online platforms in various formats, such as PDFs, images, text, and illusions. The laptop has become a home library, and smartphones have become personal libraries. Thousands of books can be stored in such gadgets in the form of Gigabits. With advanced technology like AI, these gadgets can search for appropriate information within seconds through online platforms; anyone can get related information with the help of keywords. Moreover, desired students may learn other courses online without the need to go to physical classes. They can search, apply for jobs, and attend virtual interviews through smartphones.

Background on Smartphone Usage

As per Newzoo's Global Mobile Market Report, 2021 June, 2679.54 million (267.9 crores) people use smartphones worldwide; this number belongs to only the top ten countries among smartphone users. According to population size, China is first place, followed by India and then the USA. Pakistan is in 10th place. As per smartphone penetration, the USA is in first place with 81.6 percent, Japan is in second with 78.6 percent, Russia is in third place with 71.6 percent, and India is in eighth place with 46.5 percent. Now, in 2023, this has increased, and India has about 1.01 billion smartphone users.

Table 1: Country wise smartphone usage

Rank	Country	Smartphone users (in Millions)	Percent
1	China	974.69	68.4%
2	India	659	46.5%
3	United States	276.14	81.6%

4	Indonesia	187.70	68.1%
5	Brazil	143.43	66.6%
6	Russia	106.44	73.6%
7	Japan	97.44	78.6%
8	Nigeria	83.34	38.1%
9	Mexico	78.37	61.5%
10	Pakistan	72.99	31%

Source: <https://www.wikipedia.org/>

As per the Pew Research Center in the USA, 72% of teenagers check their phone messages and notifications upon waking up. The study also reveals that 56% of teenagers experience feelings of loneliness, distress, or anxiety when separated from their phones, and 27% are at risk of depression. Additionally, 54% of teenagers admit to spending excessive time on their smartphones. Our survey respondents show little interest in using social media for college-related information, with many preferring online study groups. While most college and university students have social media accounts, the excessive use of smartphones has its drawbacks. Although they are beneficial for communication, some individuals abuse this technology by engaging in harassment on platforms like Twitter and Facebook.

These findings support the General Aggressive Model of cyberbullying, suggesting that mobile phone addiction increases the likelihood of becoming a victim of cyberbullying in high schools (Kowalski et al., 2014). This issue is prevalent in educational institutions, including universities, in many countries, such as India, leading to student conflicts and strained community relationships. Consequently, students may spend more time on social media platforms, expressing their feelings, engaging in conflicts, and discussing non-academic matters, leading to a loss of focus during lectures.

Table 2: Age-wise distribution of smartphone users in India.

S. No.	Age	Percentage
1.	18-24 years	53%
2.	25-34 years	32.7%
3.	35-44 years	11%
4.	45-54 years	2.2%
5.	55 years and above	1.1%

Source: www.start.io

Objectives:

The primary objective of this study is to assess the impact on students who waste time in the classroom using smartphones. Many studies were conducted in the early days of mobile phone innovation. Smartphones create challenges for students, teachers, and parents. It is crucial that we do not overlook parents' concerns, as they are critical stakeholders in this issue.

The primary objectives of our study will be:

1. To know the benefits to university students with smartphones.
2. To assess the disruption in the classroom by smartphones.
3. To know gender variation in the usage of smartphones in universities.

Research Method

We collected the data using a descriptive survey and a self-created questionnaire. We randomly selected 200 students from the various departments of Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati. The questionnaire was distributed to the respondents, and we collected their answers. A few respondents were interviewed with a descriptive questionnaire and discussed on various points about using smartphones in the universities. In the study's findings, students expressed that smartphones benefit their regular studies, research, and getting information about job opportunities; with that information, they reach their career goals. The study has a few negative findings that may discourage students from using smartphones. Key findings of this study are given below:

Picture 1: Do you answer incoming calls in the classroom?

- 98 percent of the students carry their smartphones into the classroom, while two percent do not.
- 14 percent of the students switched off their smartphones, 80 percent kept silent or in vibration mode, while 4 percent kept them in regular mode.
- 71 percent of students ignored incoming calls during class; however, 9 percent will take calls if they consider them essential.

Picture 2: Did you check messages and notifications in the classroom?

- We noticed that 75 percent of the students repeatedly checked their phone messages and social media notifications in the classroom, while five percent checked in leisure periods or intervals.
- 95 percent of students agree they would benefit from using smartphones around the university campus. 96 percent of respondents felt that student life is incomplete without their smartphone.

Picture 3: Do you feel disrupted by the phone ringing in the classroom?

- Only 56 percent of students felt disturbed by ringing tones from their colleagues' phones in the classroom, 27 percent of students expressed 'no', 17 percent of students said 'can't say'.
- The study identified students using their phones to contact friends for information about classes, timings, and teacher availability on campus.
- 97 percent of female students have smartphones; they feel insecure without their smartphones at university due to road incidents; and teasing. Parents are also feeling the same.

Picture 4: Do you use a smartphone for entertainment?

- 48 percent of female and 65 percent of male students carry a smartphone for entertainment purposes, such as watching YouTube videos, making calls, and chatting on WhatsApp.

Smartphone as a learning tool

Smartphones have become an educational tool and guide for university students these days. At the same time, it is widely recognised that smartphones can be a significant source of student distraction in the classroom, impacting both students' and teachers' concentration. A smartphone is not only an educational tool but also an entertainment gadget. For this reason, many educators are hesitant to permit smartphones in lecture rooms. Smartphones have AI software, which provides students with much more academic knowledge. Only now are educational institutions allowing things like tabs and laptops. They realised smartphones' potential. but following traditional educational methods and tools only in universities did not allow full-scale use of smartphones. Smartphones will be friends to the students, good or bad; it depends on usage of way. If a student uses it in an academic or research study, definitely it will become a good friend.

For example, students can cross-check their research study with the help of Google or other educational websites, they can get better information and suggestions with AI software like ChatGPT. If any content or article is not understood due to language problems, they can easily translate it into their mother tongue with the help of Google Translate, which is available in the Google Play Store and Apple Store for free. So many online libraries are available through smartphones that students can use at any time. On the other side of the coin, smartphones are meant for all age groups; entertainment, social media platforms, and even prohibited content are also available on them, good or bad it is depending on usage. Smartphones can be highly effective, especially with the increasing availability of educational apps designed for various advanced studies. Universities should reconsider their stance on allowing smartphones in the classroom.

Conclusion

The study's primary objectives include assessing the advantages of smartphone use among university students, the disruptions caused by smartphones in the classroom, and gender-specific smartphone usage patterns in university settings. The findings suggest a dual perspective on smartphone usage, supporting its benefits for university students. At the same time, in an era characterized by rapid technological advancement aimed at streamlining processes, it is imperative not to restrict its utilization among students, who represent the architects of our future societies, nations, and global community. University students are youth who are seeking better opportunities and a future. Here, they have to decide their life goals at this age, and with this connection, they will continually search for information about jobs, professional, political, and economic. The university should support them and not spoil their desires in the name of the disruption. However, the banned content and social media platforms should be restricted in classrooms with advanced technology. Regarding female students, smartphones should be allowed in and around universities due to security reasons.

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